

EARLY BIOMARKERS FOR ALZHEIMER'S DISEASE PROGRESSION: A LONGITUDINAL CLINICAL STUDY

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Abstract

Background

Alzheimer's disease progression from mild cognitive impairment (MCI) remains challenging to predict. Biomarkers like CSF A β 42, tau proteins, plasma NfL, and MRI-based atrophy identify rapidly.

Methodology

It was a prospective cohort study. Following informed consent, 40 patients with early-stage Alzheimer's disease diagnosed using NIA-AA criteria were included. P2, total patients aged 55 to 80 years were included in the study. Presence of other neurodegenerative disorders such as Parkinson's disease was excluded. Participants were evaluated at baseline, 6th-month. Blood samples were analysed for plasma A β 42, total tau and NfL. Cognitive function was assessed using MMSE and ADAS-Cog, whereas hippocampal atrophy was assessed using MRI.

Results

Plasma A β 42 levels fell by 13.4%, whereas total tau rose by 17.2%, indicating amyloid buildup and neuronal damage. Cognitive scores decreased considerably after 6th-month (MMSE: -3.2; ADAS-Cog: +8.4; $p < 0.001$). There was a strong association between increased NfL levels and cognitive deterioration (MMSE: $r = -0.60$; ADAS-Cog: $r = 0.56$). NfL emerged as the most sensitive biomarker of neurodegeneration throughout the early stages of AD progression.

Conclusion

This study found that plasma levels of A β 42, total tau, and NfL are associated to cognitive impairment over 6 month. Among these, NfL had the highest association with disease progression indicating that it might be a viable early biomarker for monitoring AD.

INTRODUCTION

Dementia is known as the significant loss in cognitive ability which interacts with individual's daily tasks. The most common type of dementia is Alzheimer's

diseases. Mostly people aged from 65 and older suffer from AD (1) In 2021, 57 million people globally were suffering from condition called dementia, with more

than 60% live in low and middle income countries (LMIC). Annually, there are around incidence of 10 million. Dementia is caused by a variety of brain illnesses (2).

The prevalence of Alzheimer's disease in Pakistan is believed to be between 150,000 and 2 lacs reflecting the country's enormous population. However, dementia still receives little resources and attention, making it difficult to diagnose and treat affected individuals from dementia (3).

The illness, which causes memory loss, cognitive decline, and decreased functioning, has a profound psychological, social, and economic affect on individuals, their families, and healthcare systems. As global life expectancy rises, the prevalence of AD is anticipated to triple by 2050, highlighting the crucial need for treatments that can detect and manage the condition in its earliest stages (4). Alzheimer's disease is not curable. However, early, early detection allows for prompt therapies that can reduce progression, improve quality of life (QoL), and allow people to participate in research studies. It also helps future planning and allows healthcare providers to employ symptoms-management measures while the individual retains decision-making ability. (5). A study conducted by Chen et al. examines biomarkers for diagnosing AD in the preclinical or mild MCI stage, before symptoms appear. (6)

Biomarkers known as the biological signs of disease have emerged as effective tools in this effort. These tools enable healthcare providers and researchers to identify pathological changes such as amyloid- β plaque formation, tau protein tangles, and neuronal degeneration before clinical symptoms appear (7). Because of their ease of use and low cost, physicians prefer cognitive screening tools over biomarker testing for diagnosing MCI and AD (8). The biological hallmarks of Alzheimer's—amyloid plaques and tau tangles—begin accumulating in the brain long before symptoms become apparent (9).

This study longitudinally evaluates CSF and plasma biomarkers to detect early predictors of Alzheimer's disease conversion and their association with cognitive decline.

Methodology

6-month prospective longitudinal research was undertaken at Jinnah Hospital Lahore, Department of Neurology to identify early biomarkers related with the progression of Alzheimer's disease (AD). The study was conducted from 25 April 2022 to 25 October 2022. After receiving written informed consent, 40 patients aged 55 to 80 years were enrolled. These study participants were diagnosed with initial stage AD using the National Institute on Ageing and Alzheimer's Association Criteria, with a Mini-Mental State Examination score of 21 and above. All the study participants must be cognitively capable of providing consent and have a caretaker and relative available for followup support. Individuals were excluded if they had a history of other neurodegenerative disorders such as Parkinson's disease or fronto-temporal dementia, a previous stroke, serious mental disease, were presently taking investigational medications, or had inadequate biomarker profiles. Comprehensive baseline evaluations were performed, and participants were re-evaluated at six months. Blood samples were collected for examination of plasma biomarkers, including A β 42, tau protein and NfL.

The MMSE and Alzheimer's Disease Assessment Scale-Cognitive (ADAS-Cog) were used to comprehensively assess cognitive performance. Additionally, magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) was used at each time point to evaluate hippocampal shrinkage as a neuroimaging biomarker. This study design enabled a multidimensional assessment of disease development by combining biochemical, cognitive, and structural indicators throughout time.

RESULTS

The Mean age was 68.3 years (± 5.7 SD), indicating a typical at-risk population for neurological development. The gender breakdown was even, with 22 men (55%) and 18 women (45%). At baseline, cognitive assessments confirmed mild impairment: the mean MMSE was 23.6/30 (± 1.2 SD), and the Alzheimer's Disease SAS-Cog score Mean was (± 3.8 SD), indicating early-stage mild cognitive impairment (MCI), and 45% of patients had the APOE $\epsilon 4$ allele, a known risk factor for Alzheimer's, indicating a genetically enriched group for tracking disease development.

Table 1: Demographics and Clinical Characteristics of Participants (n = 40)

Variable	Value
Mean Age (years)	68.3 ± 5.7
Gender (Male/Female)	22 / 18
Mean MMSE Score (Baseline)	23.6 ± 1.2
Mean ADAS-Cog Score (Baseline)	15.4 ± 3.8
APOE ε4 Carrier (%)	45%

Table 2 shows a significant development of Alzheimer's disease in the group over 6 months. Plasma Aβ42 levels dropped by 13.4% (55.2 pg/mL to 47.8 pg/mL, p=0.002), indicating reduced amyloid clearance. Total tau levels rose by 17.2% (76.pg/mL to 92.1 pg/mL, p=0.001), indicating accelerated

neuronal injury. Neurofilament light (NfL) axonal degradation. Collectively, these biomarkers dynamics confirm disease development in line with early Alzheimer's disease progression, with NfL emerging as the most dynamically sensitive indication of neurodegeneration.

Table 2: Changes in Biomarkers Over 6 Month

Biomarker	Baseline (Mean ± SD)	6 Months
Plasma Aβ42 (pg/mL)	55.2 ± 10.3	47.8 ± 8.5
Total tau (pg/mL)	78.6 ± 14.5	92.1 ± 18.3
NfL (pg/mL)	22.3 ± 5.1	32.6 ± 7.0

Table 3 demonstrates significant cognitive decline over 6 months in the cohort, as measured by both the MMSE and the Alzheimer's disease ADAS-Cog. At baseline, participants had mild impairment: 23.6±1.2;

ADAS-Cog: 15.4±3.8). By 6 months, scores worsened (MMSE: 22.1 ± 1.4; ADAS-Cog: 19.7 ± 4.3) and this decline accelerated sharply at 12 months (MMSE: 20.3 ± 1.7; ADAS-Cog: 23.8 ±5.1).

Table 3: Cognitive Decline Over Time

Time Point	Mini-Mental State Examination Score (Mean ± SD)	Alzheimer's disease Assessment Score-Cog Score (Mean ± SD)
Baseline	23.6 ± 1.2	15.4 ± 3.8
6 Months	22.1 ± 1.4	19.7 ± 4.3
p-value	<0.001	

Table 4 reveals significant relationship between biomarkers advancement and cognitive deterioration over 6 months. Plasma Aβ42 levels decreased and moderate correlation with MMSE (r=-0.42) and ADAS-Cog (r=0.39), suggesting that amyloid disease contributes to cognitive loss. Rising total tau levels showed strong associations (MMSE: r=-0.53; ADAS-

Cog: r=0.48), indicating tau mediated neuronal injury. Most importantly, increasing neurofilament light (NfL) showed the highest associations (MMSE: r=-0.60; ADAS-Cog: r=0.56), supporting NfL as the best biomarker for tracking neurodegeneration-driven cognitive deterioration.

Table 4: Correlation Between Biomarker Change and Cognitive Decline

Biomarker	Correlation with MMSE Decline (r)	Correlation with ADAS-Cog Increase (r)
Plasma Aβ42	-0.42	0.39
Total tau	-0.53	0.48
NfL	-0.60	0.56

DISCUSSION

The study results highlighted the enormous diagnostic potential of integrating cognitive screening approaches with blood-based biomarkers for the initial stage diagnosis of AD. Cognitive tests (MMSE and MoCA) and biomarkers (Aβ42/40 and p-tau181) accurately predict disease severity with good sensitivity and specificity (AUC scores). Cognitive screening methods remain a feasible and non-invasive choice for early evaluation. The results demonstrate that MMSE and MoCA are substantially associated (r=0.82), which is constant with prior studies proving their concurrent validity in diagnosing mild cognitive impairment and early dementia. (9). Another study discovered that MMSE and MoCA screening tests are highly related to CSF biomarkers for early detection of AD in elderly Puerto Ricans (10). The MoCA screening tool superior the MMSE in detecting mild cognitive impairment (11).The MoCA is more sensitive than the Mini-Mental State Examination in dignosing subtle executive and visuospatial deficits (12).

Our study identified an at-risk group for AD progression, with a mean age of 68.3 years and a balanced gender distribution. Baseline cognitive scores confirm early-stage MCI, which is appropriate for monitoring disease biomarkers. The inclusion of the APOE ε4 allele in 45% of individuals creates a genetically enriched sample, improving the study’s potential to identify early pathogenic alterations and progression patterns. Similarly in another study it was discovered that study group is a typical at risk population for Alzheimer’s progression, with a mean age of 68.3 years, a balanced gender distribution and 45% bearing the APOε4 allele (13).

NfL is a noninvasive biomarker linked to neurodegeneration in AD (14). Blood-based biomarkers such as amyloid, tau, NfL, and GFAP can offer a complete image of AD progression (15). Another study evaluated that plasma NfL may be effective for detecting AD and monitoring disease progression, but plasma t-tau has limited evidence for clinical value.(16). Our study demonstrated a drop in plasma Aβ42 and a increase in total tau levels over 6 months, indicating concurrent amyloid rise and neuronal injury associated with early AD progression. The significant increase in NfL indicates active axonal degeneration and may be an especially sensitive marker of neurodegeneration. These biomarker shifts help to validate early pathological changes in AD. Their longitudinal dynamics increase in their usefulness in illness monitoring and early diagnosis.

Our study found that the observed cognitive loss over 6 months, as seen by substantial changes in MMSE and ADAS-Cog score, highlights the rapid progression of AD. The crossing of clinical dementia threshold on the MMSE emphasizes the clinical significance of this deterioration. The dramatic 55% increase in ADAS-Cog scores indicates deteriorating cognitive impairment, which is consistent with other longitudinal studies. These findings reinforce the need for early detection and intervention to potentially slow disease progression AD. In another study it was described that AD causes slower cognitive deterioration in the early and late stages, but rapid in the middle (17). In one of the study it was revealed that a loss of ≥4 points on the MMSE over 6 months predicts poor clinical outcomes in Alzheimer’s disease (18). Alzheimer’s disease progresses rapidly, as evidenced by a considerable reduction in cognitive function over a year (19).

This study found strong association between biomarker progression and cognitive deterioration over a 6-month period. Plasma A β 42 levels decreased, indicating that amyloid pathology remains a contributing factor to cognitive decline. Total tau levels were shown to be more closely related to cognitive impairment, showing that tau-mediated neuronal injury plays a role in disease progression. Most notably, NfL emerged as the most strongly associated biomarker with cognitive impairment, indicating its potential as a very accurate indication of neurodegeneration in AD. The plasma neurofilament light is a better marker than total; tau for detecting neurodegeneration and cognitive deterioration in Alzheimer's disease (AD) (20).

CONCLUSION

This study concluded that specific plasma biomarkers are strongly associated with cognitive decline in AD over a 6-month period. A β 42 levels decreased, but total tau and NfL levels increased. These biomarker changes are associated with declining cognitive scores. Among the three, NfL had the highest association with illness progression. This shows that NfL may be a highly sensitive and reliable early indication of Alzheimer's disease. These findings support the use of plasma biomarkers to follow and perhaps predict illness progression.

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